

Groupoid of OEIS A001844 Numbers (centered square numbers)

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Italy.

Here we discuss the binary operator of the set made by the OEIS sequence of integers A001844, defined as centered square numbers. This binary operator can be used to have a groupoid. Actually, neutral and opposite elements can be defined too, and a possible group for these numbers can be given.

Written in Torino, 19 June 2019. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3250268. Revised 22 June 2019. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3252339

A groupoid is an algebraic structure made by a set with a binary operator [1]. The only restriction on the operator is closure. This properties means that, applying the binary operator to two elements of a given set S, we obtain a value which is itself a member of S. If this operation is associative and we have a neutral element and opposite elements into the set, then the groupoid becomes a group.

Here, we consider the set of numbers given by OEIS sequence A001844 (centered square numbers). The numbers have the following form [2]:

$$C_n = n^2 + (n+1)^2 = 2n(n+1) + 1$$

As we did in some previous discussions (see for instance [3-5]), we can find a binary operator, which satisfy the closure. Let us follow the same approach as in [5], for Carol and Kynea numbers.

We have: $C_n = n^2 + (n+1)^2 = 2n(n+1) + 1 = 2(n+1/2)^2 + 1/2$.

Let us use numbers A_n , so that: $(n+1/2)^2 = (A_n)^2$.

$$[(C_m - 1/2)/2]^{1/2} = (m+1/2) = A_m \quad ; \quad [(C_n - 1/2)/2]^{1/2} = (n+1/2) = A_n \quad ;$$

$$[(C_{m+n} - 1/2)/2]^{1/2} = (m+n+1/2) = A_{m+n}$$

Numbers A_m can help us in the calculation (the same numbers we used in [6]).

For them, the binary operator is:

$$A_{m+n} = A_m \oplus A_n = A_m + A_n - 1/2 = (m+1/2) + (n+1/2) - 1/2 = m+n+1/2$$

Therefore:

$$[(C_{m+n}-1/2)/2]^{1/2}=(m+n+1/2)=A_{m+n} = A_m \oplus A_n = A_m + A_n - 1/2$$

Consequently, for the centered square numbers, the binary operator of a generalized sum is coming from:

$$C_{m+n}=C_m+C_n+2(C_m-1/2)^{1/2}(C_n-1/2)^{1/2}-\sqrt{2}(C_m-1/2)^{1/2}-\sqrt{2}(C_n-1/2)^{1/2}$$

The generalized sum is given as:

$$C_m \oplus C_n = C_m + C_n + 2(C_m - 1/2)^{1/2}(C_n - 1/2)^{1/2} - \sqrt{2}(C_m - 1/2)^{1/2} - \sqrt{2}(C_n - 1/2)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

From (1), we have the recursive relation: $C_{n+1} = C_n \oplus C_1$. Starting with number $C_1 = 5$, we have: 13, 25, 41, 61, 85, 113, 145, 181, 221, 265, 313, 365, 421, 481, 545, 613, 685, 761, 841, 925, and so on. The same as <http://oeis.org/A001844>.

The binary operator is associative: $C_{m+n+p} = C_{m+n} \oplus C_p = C_m \oplus C_{n+p}$

Using (1), we can see that we can have a neutral element: $C_0 = 1$.

$$C_{m+0} = C_m \oplus C_0 = C_m + C_0 + 2(C_m - 1/2)^{1/2}(C_0 - 1/2)^{1/2} - \sqrt{2}(C_m - 1/2)^{1/2} - \sqrt{2}(C_0 - 1/2)^{1/2}$$

$$C_m + 1 + 2(C_m - 1/2)^{1/2}(1/2)^{1/2} - \sqrt{2}(C_m - 1/2)^{1/2} - \sqrt{2}(1/2)^{1/2} = C_m$$

Since we have a neutral element, we could try to find the opposite element so that:

$$C_{m-m} = C_m \oplus Opp(C_m) = C_m \oplus C_{-m} = C_0$$

In [2], we have the relation: $a(-m) = a(m-1)$ (*), where $a(m) = C_m$.

Let us consider, in the framework given above, the meaning of (*).

Let us define $X = \sqrt{(Opp(C_m) - 1/2)}$ and evaluate

$$C_0 = C_m \oplus Opp(C_m) = C_m + X^2 + 1/2 + 2X(C_m - 1/2)^{1/2} - \sqrt{2}(C_m - 1/2)^{1/2} - \sqrt{2}X = 1 \quad (**)$$

This is an equation of the form $X^2 + BX + K = 0$, where coefficients are:

$$B = 2(C_m - 1/2)^{1/2} - \sqrt{2} \quad \text{and} \quad K = C_m + 1/2 - 1 - \sqrt{2}(C_m - 1/2)^{1/2}.$$

Solutions are given by $X = (-B \pm \sqrt{(B^2 - 4K)})/2$, where $\sqrt{(B^2 - 4K)} = \sqrt{2}$.

For $X = (-B - \sqrt{2})/2$, the opposite element turns out to be: $Opp(C_m) = C_m$. We have therefore that the composition (**) of an element with itself produces the identity. So each element turns out to be self-inverse.

For $X = (-B + \sqrt{2})/2$, the opposite element is given as:

$$Opp(C_m) = X^2 + 1/2 = C_{m-1}$$

and therefore we find relation (*). However, in the binary operation (**), X is negative.

As a consequence, when we use C_{m-1} in the generalized sum (1), if we assume the negative value of root $X = -\sqrt{(C_{m-1} - 1/2)}$, we obtain the neutral element, so that $C_m \oplus C_{-m} = C_0$. In the case that we use the positive root, the generalized sum gives $C_m \oplus C_{m-1} = C_{2m-1}$. The reason is that, to find (1), we could use a positive or negative sign in front of the square root:

$$\pm[(C_{m-1} - 1/2)/2]^{1/2} = (m - 1 + 1/2) = A_{m-1}$$

If we want to use the binary operator for a groupoid, it is enough to use the positive value of the root.

References

- [1] Stover, Christopher and Weisstein, Eric W. "Groupoid." From MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/Groupoid.html>
- [2] oeis.org/A001844
- [3] Sparavigna, Amelia Carolina. (2019, April 9). On the generalized sums of Mersenne, Fermat, Cullen and Woodall Numbers. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2634312>
- [4] Sparavigna, Amelia Carolina (2019). Composition Operations of Generalized Entropies Applied to the Study of Numbers, International Journal of Sciences 8(04): 87-92. DOI: 10.18483/ijSci.2044
- [5] Sparavigna, Amelia Carolina. (2019, June 6). Binary Operators of the Groupoids of OEIS A093112 and A093069 Numbers (Carol and Kynea Numbers). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3240465>
- [6] Sparavigna, Amelia Carolina. (2019, June 16). Groupoids of OEIS A002378 and A016754 Numbers (oblong and odd square numbers). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3247003>